

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

SPACE AS A UNIVERSAL EPISTEMOLOGICAL CATEGORY: MATERIAL AND IMMATERIAL (SPECULATIVE) SPACE

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Abstract

The main purpose of the article is to focus on the analysis of the fundamental scientific-philosophical category of space, which plays an extremely important role in human life and cognitive processes, in the context of modern innovations. Although there are a large number of studies that explore certain aspects of the concept of space and define it as a universal episteme as a whole, the features of its existence in all their complexity and completeness have not yet been fully integrated into philosophical ontology. In this regard, the constant increase in dynamically changing scientific knowledge in the 21st century, the relativity of space, its relationship with time and matter constantly require new interpretation in philosophical terms.

Keywords: material (place-denoting) space, immaterial (speculative) space, social space, multidimensional space, fractal space, virtual space

Introduction. Space is the most important and fundamental scientific and philosophical category. It plays an extremely important role in human life and cognitive processes. There are two fundamentally different ontological types of spaces: a single world of material space and multiple immaterial (speculative) spaces created by intersubjective and subjective intellectual activity and endowed with common meanings.

The constantly increasing and dynamically changing scientific knowledge in the 21st century, the relativity of space, its relationship with time and matter, constantly require new interpretation in philosophical terms. Although in the first half and middle of the last century, physical laws in the macro and micro worlds were widely discussed in natural science, as well as in philosophy, the new results of post-non-classical science, ideas about the possible multidimensionality and discreteness of space, the fractality of various giant spatial objects, the features of the existence of virtual spaces have not yet been integrated into philosophical ontology in all their complexity and completeness.

Main matters. It is true that there are many studies that explore certain aspects of the concept of space and define it as a universal episteme as a whole. Space was first described mathematically and physically by I. Newton as an infinite space in which the universe exists. He laid the foundation for scientific ideas about absolute space and the classical scientific paradigm.

The formation of a non-classical scientific paradigm is based on A. Einstein's concept of space. Einstein considers space as a universal but relative phenomenon associated with time, matter, energy and geometry as objects move.

Today, the problem of creating a post-non-classical spatial ontology based on modern scientific results is extremely relevant and important. There is no doubt that this can only be implemented within the framework of philosophical ontology, and its results will have not only theoretical, but also practical

significance in the future.

In philosophical works, the concept of space in the ontological sense is presented as one of the universal principles or as a universal phenomenon that determines human existence. It should be noted that in European philosophy, beginning with antiquity, there are practically no philosophical systems that would not use the concept of space and would not try to define space in one way or another. Greek philosophers Pythagoras, Leucippus, Democritus, Plato, Aristotle, as well as N. Kuzansky, F. Bacon, G. Galileo, R. Descartes, G. Hegel, B. Spinoza considered space as a universal metaphysical being, a substance with certain properties. K. Berkeley, D. Hume, G. Leibniz, I. Kant represented space as a universal form of human worldview and rational knowledge. Euclid was the first to put forward the idea of the three-dimensionality of real space and defined a rectangular coordinate system as its main feature. Later, I. Lobachevsky, B. Riemann, E. Beltrami, F. Klein, G. Minkowski constructed curvilinear geometric systems that allowed them to describe the properties of real space.

The meaning of the concept of space that emerged in antiquity is connected with large ontological and epistemological systems. In this regard, historical analysis allows us to confirm that Platon's ideas about cosmos and space were very important for the entire subsequent philosophical tradition.

It was from Platon's ideas that the tradition of considering space as the eternal container of all that exists, "the abode of all that is born," began, which later developed into the concept of absolute space. The tradition of defining space not as something in itself, but as something else, something that can actually be discovered through relationships, is also associated with Platon (8, p. 29). In particular, it should be noted that researchers usually consider Platon to be the founder and successor of the concept of substantial space.

Aristotle was the first to include space among the

10 fundamental categories and practically identified the universal meaning of space with the idea of "place" in his ontology (2, p.76). He defined space as a boundary surrounding an object. Aristotle also speaks of the three-dimensionality of space: the world is an object that has length, width, and depth. Similarly, Leucippus and Democritus understood space as a container, considering it to be "emptiness." Democritus' space is an independent entity, a substance independent of matter, an objective, homogeneous, infinite void that exists in reality and contains the entire collection of atoms. Descartes believed that the world was a continuum filled with material objects. Descartes also defined the structure of space as determined by the motion of material bodies. He emphasized that since there is no vacuum and all bodies are in contact, the motion of one of them causes the motion of all the others. This defines the curvilinear geometry of the motion of material objects (3, p.52).

Galileo says that if we divide a body into a finite number of parts, and if we divide each divided part again, there will certainly be nothing left of them before. In this case, the body will occupy a larger volume than the original. We can imagine such components extending into a huge space, covering unlimited empty spaces, an infinite number of voids devoid of their initial size. Galileo thereby shows the three-dimensionality and homogeneity of space, as a result of which he gives the idea of space as a curved closed empty container of the world.

Spinoza noted the existence of a spatial dimension for all material objects that allowed them to be compared. This was a reference to the concept of relativity of space.

In the works of G. Leibniz, the ideas about the relativity of space and time are finally formalized, and space is conceived precisely as the mutual order of everything that exists. According to Leibniz, space is not a reality that exists in itself, but phenomena that arise from the existence of other realities. There is no "pure" space "in itself" and, therefore, there is no emptiness. Space is the order of placing objects, juxtaposing phenomena, which, by their co-existence, acquire a certain place relative to each other (1, p. 76). The idea of the mutual order of space can also be perceived as a logical consequence of Hegel's ideas. For Hegel, space is in an inseparable dialectical relationship with time, motion and matter. He said that only in motion are space and time valid, but just as there is no motion without matter, there is no matter without motion. Space itself is static and at the same time both continuous and discrete.

Thus, the second, and also quite clear, meaning of space opens up: space is the order of the existence of objects in the world. It has two important semantic meanings: 1) space as a container for everything that exists, as a place – the simplest and most intuitively understandable meaning associated with the existence of things; 2) space as the order of the existence of objects in the world – a more complex, in our opinion, meaning directly related to the possibility of knowing the properties of things (5, p. 98).

Kant interprets space as an a priori, "pure" form of

any visual representation, a form of sensory intuition. For Kant, space is a pure visual representation, outside of empirical experience. Kant's epistemological doctrine of a priori forms of thought echoes Platon's ontology. According to Kant, as well as to Platon, spatial representations are a fundamental feature of human consciousness and determine the person's ability to best understand the world. This is a "coordinate network" that is useful for cognition, allowing the cognitive subject to understand the relationships of objects and to discuss them with other interested subjects.

A person without spatial representations cannot comprehend the world. Kant expanded the idea that was too narrow for science by presenting space as a universal form of the existence of the material world (8, p. 45). Such a view became the philosophical basis for the wide application of spatial concepts in various kinds of theoretical constructions, the creation of "speculative", immaterial spaces, for example, mathematical or social spaces, and provided a unique heuristic method for a wide range of research. Later, Schopenhauer also joined Kant's teaching on the subjectivity and a priori nature of space. The only difference in their views is that for Schopenhauer, space cannot be conceived in itself and can only be conceived when it is filled with matter as an object of sense. He defined space as a form of individual consciousness.

In our opinion, we have come to an important conclusion: the difference between the substantial (ontological) and cognitive (epistemological) meanings of space can be reduced to fundamentally different answers to the question of the reality of its existence. The discussion of positive and negative views on the existence of space as a material reality continued until the beginning of the 20th century, until the creation of the theory of relativity. The category of "space" became such an important episteme that it became the rule for those sciences to locate not only material, physical, but also immaterial, mental, and speculative objects. The existence of many speculative spaces defines space as one of the two main (the other being time) cognitive strategies, as a general scientific episteme that allows for the optimal ordering of objects in a given cognitive domain. Cognition with the help of speculative spaces involves the visualization of intangible or invisible entities in reality, the mental reflection of the intangible.

The most important speculative space is social space. Social space is conceived as a part of real geographical spaces and is described by terms such as "social distance" and "social volume", which have geometric and mechanical analogues. Social space is epistemologically indeterminate. The study of its structure allows us to determine not only the order and relationships of social phenomena, but also their important features. As a result, the concept of social space, which has enormous heuristic and epistemological potential, and the concepts of economic, political, historical and cultural spaces arising from it, are formed.

Like physical space, social space is interpreted ambiguously in the humanities and social sciences. On

the one hand, social space is conceived as part of real physical or geographical spaces that serve as an arena for human activity and a container for real society. According to this view, physical space, created by the will of the Creator or by natural causes, is transformed into social space as a result of human activity, filled with social subjects and objects and develops. Social space is studied by Weber primarily as a social phenomenon located within certain spatial boundaries in the context of urban space. G. Simmel views social space as a specially organized geographical space. Social space is associated with social groups living in a certain area. Social space is created precisely due to the energy of the activity of subjects, and each part of social space is unique (11, p.34).

B. Russell believed that there are concepts that we perceive only as occurring in physical space. Positivist interpretations directly transfer the properties of physical space to the properties of social space. Following this, social dynamics, founded by O. Comte, works with analogues of classical mechanical quantities (11, p.75). Thus, social space is perceived primarily as a real place where people live, a socialized physical space that acquires special, non-physical properties due to social practices.

This space is three-dimensional and its topology is determined by the geographical landscape, settlement patterns and social practices, but it always resembles the topology of physical space to some extent, and therefore we can speak of its geometric properties. On the other hand, a more complex idea of social space emerges as a speculative multidimensional space of functionally interconnected social processes, social relations, social practices, social positions and social fields.

Currently, in the social sciences, social space is primarily defined as a speculative space formed by an ensemble of subspaces (for example, political, economic, cultural, historical) with a complex multidimensional topology and non-trivial structure. Let us immediately note that the identification of subspaces of social space indicates a very popular and heuristic tendency for the study of any, even local, social processes. This has led to a significant divergence of ideas about social space (family space, school space, university space, theater space, etc.).

Conclusions. Thus, it was shown that with the help of the concept of speculative space, cognition involves the visualization of intangible or invisible

entities in reality, the mental reflection of the intangible. The most important speculative space is social space, epistemologically indefinite, and it is conceived as part of real geographical spaces.

In the post-non-classical scientific paradigm, the most important properties of space are characterized by the uncertainty of topological and metric properties, as well as multidimensionality, fractality, and virtuality.

Currently, the nonlinear picture of the world is becoming increasingly complex. Today, the world is more complex than was recently imagined. The world, possessing a complex ontological structure, is subject to universal synergetic laws of development, and processes of self-organization and chaos constantly alternate throughout evolution. This nonlinear, dynamic, ontologically multifaceted world, caught in countless feedback loops, is extremely complex to study, and uncertainty is incorporated into its cognitive process as an important, integral feature.

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